

**PERSONAL CULTURE AND PERSONAL
CIVIL CULTURE**

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ANNOTATION

The article compares personal culture and personal civil culture. The interdependence of personal culture and society culture and the formation of structural structures of personal culture have been studied. Attention is paid to the fact that these components are the basis of the civil culture of the individual.

Key words: Personality, culture, personality culture, personality civil culture, political culture, economic culture, legal culture, moral culture, aesthetic culture, ecological culture.

INTRODUCTION

Culture is an extremely comprehensive concept, which vividly expresses their activity as an integral component of the life of a person, society and state. In the structure of culture, the civil culture of the individual is especially important, and it reflects the activities of the individual in economic, political and social life.

The "individualized society" is becoming more and more distant from the interests of the Motherland and society, and this process has a profound effect on his social activity. In this regard, there is a need to adapt the civil culture of the individual to the new social reality. First of all, it is necessary to describe and analyze the scientific concepts of personal culture and personal civil culture.

LITERATURE AND METHOD

From the works of A.Spirkin and Q.Nazarov in the description of culture, personal culture and social culture, S.Choriev and A. Zhigulin studies were used. Logical methods such as analysis and synthesis, complex approach, structural-functional analysis, comparative analysis, and generalization were also used.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULT

It is known that "culture is understood as a set of material and spiritual values, as well as the methods of their creation, their use in the path of human development, the skills of passing them from ancestors to generations"[1, C.762].

Usually experts classify culture into material and spiritual culture. In this case, material culture refers to the means of production and objects of work, and spiritual culture refers to science, the level of literacy of the population, enlightenment in society, medical services, the state of art, norms of behavior, spiritual needs of members of society, and so on [1, C .762]. However, all these considerations apply to the culture of society. In addition, there is another form of culture - personal culture. Personal culture is a concept that expresses the sum of knowledge and imagination of a person about material and spiritual values, the degree of mastering the methods of their creation, and the skill of using them. The word culture, - writes Q. Nazarov, the Arabic word "madina" and "iyat" is formed from the addition of the formative suffix, and it means "belonging to the city". Probably under the influence of the fact that cities have become centers of science and enlightenment, it began to be used in the languages of a number of nations, including Uzbek, in the sense of enlightenment, knowledge, education"[2, B.686].

Enlightenment, knowledge, education are the basis of personal culture. Since the knowledge and imagination of a person is related to different forms of existence, different spheres of social life, personal culture is classified into such forms as political culture, legal culture, moral culture, religious culture, aesthetic culture, economic culture, ecological culture.

However, civil culture is not a separate form of personal culture. The civil culture of a person is a concept that includes the character of his political, legal,

moral, religious, spiritual, economic, ecological and other cultures, personal ideas and values, acquired knowledge and ideas, and the part of the norms of his activity that are in accordance with the interests of the Motherland and society. For example, political culture "represents stable components of political activity and political consciousness"[3, B.220]. Political knowledge, political thinking, political values, political norms, political activity, etc. can be recognized as components. The part of this knowledge, values and norms that is in the interests of the Motherland and society constitutes the civil culture of an individual.

The legal culture of a person shows the level of formation of his legal consciousness (legal knowledge, ideas, values) and activity[4, C.98]. Civil culture embodies the responsibility of the individual for the fate of the Motherland, the legal knowledge and ideas that represent the duties and obligations before the society, and the directions of legal activity in the interests of the Motherland and society. The moral culture of a person means, on the one hand, his knowledge and ideas about morality, on the other hand, his moral values, and on the third hand, moral norms that encourage him to act in one way or another. Moral knowledge, imagination, values and norms that encourage to act in accordance with the interests of the country and society take place in its civil culture.

The economic culture of a person is a product of the organic unity of consciousness and practical activity that determines the creative direction of a person's economic activity in the process of production, distribution and consumption. If we take into account that economic thinking plays an important role in the economic culture of a person, then knowing the essence of economic events and processes, using the acquired economic knowledge in the perspective of the economic development of the country, analyzing specific economic situations and ensuring the stable development of the country ensures that it takes place in the structure of civil culture.

Today, religious culture is the faith of people formed under the influence of religion, the traditions of worshipping God and living, which is reflected in their material and spiritual activities. Religious culture is complex, which means that, firstly, each religion (there are about 3000 religions) promotes different norms, secondly, each religion is comprehensive and includes all areas of society, and thirdly, the social norms of religion affect all layers of society and the highest and penetrates to the lowest systems. A person's religious culture is a combination of existing norms in religion and religious norms that he (the believer) is implementing.

As religion provides a holistic picture of the world for people, including the religious norms and criteria that are considered the basis for unifying and directing the system, it also forms the basis of the civil culture of the individual.

Aesthetic culture refers to the material, political, social and cultural spheres that have arisen in the course of historical development, to satisfy the aesthetic needs of a person as a social subject. Humanistic, universal ideas and ideals, which form the basis of personal aesthetic culture - mastering the world based on the laws and standards of beauty, occupy a central place in personal civil culture.

Environmental culture of a person is formed in a responsible person who can see, recognize and seek solutions to environmental problems. Environmental culture of a person is a part of civil culture, when a citizen always cares for and protects mother nature in his activities, as well as feels responsible for solving environmental problems. The principles of personal ecological culture, such as ecological value, ecological duty, ecological compatibility, ecological cooperation and ecological sustainability, are important components of personal civic culture.

CONCLUSION

So, the relationship between the forms of personal culture and civil culture can be described as follows:

A person's culture embodies his knowledge and imagination, ideas and values, activity norms related to political, legal, ethical, religious, aesthetic, labor, environmental and other fields. This knowledge and imagination, norms will have a different character. Only the part of them that is in the interest of the

Motherland and society constitutes the civil culture of the individual. In turn, the interaction between political, legal, moral, religious, aesthetic, economic, ecological cultures and civil culture acquires a dialectical character.

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